

DEVA PRASHNA DONE BY ME – A STUDY

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Abstract:

In this article we understand what devaprashnam and the steps of devaprashnam very well. It is very helpful to improve the divinity of God. In Kerala it is following as a traditional method. We can easily understand the plus and minus of the particular temple. If we find any curse we will easily remove it through pooja parihar.

Key Words: Pricha – Prasna Kriya – Deepa Lakshana – Chakra Lekhana – Prama Neetham – Suthram – Thri Spudam Asta Mangala Things – Swarna Arooa – Deva Bhava – Sathur Spudam – Pancha Spudam – Chozhi Prasna – Threkkannam – Thamboola Prana – Chozhi Prasna

Introduction:

There are so many prasanna marga for human beings like Jamakkol prasannam, Asta mangala prasannam etc. Similary deva prasannam is only for god. It conveys the result the god is power or not. Any dosha is in the temple it indicates the status of the king, country, people and the god.

My Deva Prashnam:

Pricha:

The important persons of the temple like the president, Dharma kartha, executive officer, commissioner should come to the Acharya's house or office, call him to do deva Prashna to their temple. At that time the Acharya calculate the time, hora, lagna of the certain time. It tells about the condition of the temple. The star doing pricha must be good. Avoid pricha on Tuesday and Saturday. One who came on Tuesday for pricha he has the fear of death. Pricha always done on morning only. Never done it afternoon. Athiyanoor kottiyal Sree Mahadevar Temple Thiruvananthapuram

Daivakjan –

Kolla Varsham – 1196 – Kumbham – 13th 2021 Feb 25th Thursday

Udayalparam 3 nazhika 5 vinazhika morning IST 7.58 hr am

Pushyam star Shukla Paksha Trayodashi Gardhapa karana

Shobhana nithya yogam in Cherthala house Pricha happened.

Four concern people came with furits, betels, areca nut and money

Udaya Laknam (Ascendant) – Meenam

Swasam – Vama sharam

Bhuothodaya – Vayu

Grashodayam - Vyazham

Prashnaksharam – 22 Maruth

ASC	MANTHI	MARS RAHU	
SUN VENUS	RASI		MOON
MERCURY JUPITER SATURN			
	KETU		

		SATURN	MERCURY
	NAVAMSA		JUPITER RAHU
SUN MERCURY KETHU			ASC
	MOON VENUS	MANTHI	

Nirgamam:

This denotes the time when the Acharya starts his visit to the temple from his home. Hora is very important for this event. Jupiter, hora, venus hora and Mercury hora are very auspicious for this Jupiter aspected lagnas are also favour. Prasna kartha telling first word is very very important. The word starts with vowel is good. The word starts with consonant is bad.

From the house started traveling on shubha hora (Guru hora).

Nimitham – Cow coming towards Daivakjan with it's calf

Margam:

When the Acharya's journey to the temple, he should watch each and every movement, Nimitham, omen etc. He feels his happiness sorrows and difficulties from start his home to reach the temple. It is very important. If the Acharya sees any negative omen he should return to home. Do pranayama breathing exercise. Then he goes again. Again he sees any negative omen he should cancell his programme. Crossing cat, snake, monkey is bad omen. Seeing disabled person. Sick patient, mad, blind man, single brahmin is also ill omen.

Double brahmin, sumangali, virgn, waterful pot are good omen.

Reached the temple without difficulties

Mandiragathi:

Acharya is received proper by the VIP's of the temple. They give him a warm welcome. First Acharya walk on the steps. Others follow him in back side. Received properly, entered the main door followed by others.

At the time of Acharya' entry a thing is broken or fall down, hearing crying is very bad.

Received properly, entered the main door followed by others.

Prashnakriya Sambhavam:

Prashna'riya held kollvarsham - 1197 - Vrshika masam 06th 21 nov 2021 sunday after sunrise 13 nazhika 35 vinazhika IST 11.47 am to know Athiyannur Sree Mahadeva temple main Deva all updeva's blessing to the bhaktha and neighboring peoples and all good and bad things above the temple related peoples held deva prashna

Pradamaneeethi (First Tech Item):

One of the VIP'S touch any one thing from the 8 mangala things. It helps us to take prediction.

Thumbha poo (White colour flower)

Deepam Lakshanam:

Here the Acharya notices

- Which oil is used to light the lamp?
- Which wick and howmany wicks are used?
- Which direction the deepam shined?
- Is ghee used for it?

We can easily tell about their family by the total number of wicks. Panchavarthi neyy deepam (five flamed ghee lamp) start from east clockwise poorvavarthi prarambham pradakishinam.

Chakralekhanam:

Here Acharya asks one to draw rasi chakra. He notices the starting point from east to west / west to east / south to North / North to south. He also notices the drawing position is clock wise or anti clock wise. This will help him to identify the problem.

Poorvarekha pranbham pradakshinam (east line first clockwise)

Uthrarekha aprathikshanam (south line second anticlockwise)

Pashchimarekha aprathikshanam (west line third anticlockwise)

Dakshinarekha aprathikshanam (north line fourth anticlockwise)

Prashnavakyam (Prashna Word):

Now the Acharya asks one of the VIP'S to utter a word. Then he notes it and take prediction. He counts the total letters of the word. Then he do neivedya.

"Dhakshina swekarikkanam"

Udayarashi (Ascendant) – Makarasashi

Swarnaroodam – Makararashi

Ponpanasthithi (Gold Coin Position):

The Acharya says the child to round the rasi chakra 3 times then put the gold coin on the rasi chakra. The child will do it perfectly. Here the Acharya see the position of the gold coin. It is straight / up / down / slanting. The direction should also watch by the Acharya.

Center of pushppakshatham (mixture of rice, paddy, chandan and flower

invertedly slanting towards east.

Swarnarashi amshakam - Midhunarashi

Shwasam:

The Acharya checks his breath. Is this pinkala nadi (right nose) or idakala nadi (left nose) or susumna nadi (same time, from both nose). It helps him to predict the problem. Vasi yogam is very must for Acharya. Prasna kartha stands in front of the Acharya or left side of Acharya is very good in sukla paksha. Similarly prasnakartha stands back side of the Acharya or right side of the Acharya is best for krishna paksha.

Dhakshinasharam

Sparsham:

The Acharya touches his left hand with the right hand and do divine mudras to connect the God.

Touched left hand with right hand

Ashttamangala Sankhya:

The Acharya divides the 108 chozhies into 3 Then he takes 8 chozhis again and again from each group. Finally he calculate the balance in each group and notes them for predication.

Thamboola Graham:

The Acharya count the total betal leaf given by the dharma kartha. Then he multiplies this with 2. Again he multiplies the answer with 5. Then add 1 with the answer. Finally the divided the number with seven to find the balance.

First multiply number 2 denotes father and mother. Next multiply number 5 denotes five elements or panjabootha. Then the addiing number 1 denotes the soul

Which is Called Aathma?

If the balance number is

- The thamboola graha is Sun
- The thamboola graha is Moon
- The thamboola graha is Mars
- The thamboola graha is Mercury
- The thamboola graha is Jupiter
- The thamboola graha is Venus
- The thamboola graha is Saturn
- The thamboola graha is Jupiter

Thamboola Aroodam:

Thamboola graha's standing rasi is called thamboola aruda lagna.

Kumbham (Aquaris)

Sphudangal Calculations:

Rashi	Bhaga	Kala	
09	22	29	Udayaroodam (Ascendant)
07	04	59	Sun
01	25	23	Moon
06	20	31	Mars
07	00	28	Mercury
10	00	03	Jupiter
08	19	37	Venus
09	14	06	Saturn
01	07	31	Rahu
07	07	31	Ketu
00	10	44	Manthi
		Thri Sphudam	
11	28	36	
		Chath Sphudam	
07	03	35	
		Pancha Sphudam	
08	11	06	
		Prana Sphudam	
01	03	09	
		Dheha Sphudam	
03	03	48	
		Mrithu Sphudam	
09	20	27	
		Sookshamthri Sphudam	
01	27	04	

	MANTHI	MOON RAHU	CHATHRAM PRSHTTANG AM	RAHU	MARS	SATURN	SWARNA
JUPITER THAM BOOLAM	RASI				NAVAMSA		ASC MERCURY MANTHI
ATURN SWARNA ASC							SUN MOON
VENUS	MERCURY SUN KETU					JUPITER	VENUS KETU

Kinchith Phalam:

In past owner of the temple a Namboothiri family one of that family member has acharya sthanam in temple now the owners were changed and split into two group they are not in good terms.

- A brahmin family reside west south region of the temple
- Nagakkavu was west side of the temple.
- Deity is got tilt
- Ashttabhantha is not remaining property on water stagnant in the gap of the ashttabhantha.
- Olden days the tribes were have an important role in the temple.
- Under the Banyan tree in front of the temple there was worship of nagaraja and at the time of renovation of the temple the place changed to kanya rashi

Thamboola Chintha (Betel Leaf Examination):

First Bhava:

- Bhimbham, sannidhyam etc.
- To replace Ganapathi temple at kanya rashi
- Parvathi to dhanush rashi
- Nagaraja, Yaksh amma, Madan thamburan and sharkkara devi south side of the temple

Second Bhava:

- Some dispute with the land of temple.
- No proper governance

Third Bhava:

- Nivedhyam preparation is not in the proper way the quantity of nivedhyam is not fixed properly utensils should be made up of panchaloha
- There was to irregular death of servants of the temple

Fourth Bhava:

- Not affected

Fifth Bhava:

- Sannidhyam (presents of the god) and bhimbham

Sixth Bhava:

- Ashudhi is there in the temple lot of bhadha dosham in the temple

Seventh Bhava:

- Improve the alangaram the flowers should be pure to make mala and pooja
- Start pradasha pooja and perform Uma Maheshwara pooja

Eighth Bhava:

- Thidamb and uthsava moorthi should be placed properly

Ninth Bhava:

- Brahmana, Khaathriya, Shoodra involvement in the temple, temple land grabbed someone and kept themselves some of the temple owner family members felt in some accidents in olden days.

Tenth Bhava:

- Makara masa uthsav is important also dhanu masa thiruvathra makes special occasion should celebrate

Eleventh Bhava:

- Sukrtha kshayam in temple and related people

Twelfth Bhava:

- Poorvacharya dhosha should rectified by doing parithara karma olden days priest dhuritham brahmana shapam are also rectified by doing parihara karma all changes should do with prayaschitha parihara ashttabhantha kalasham.
- Do mandalam 41 days niramala
- Chathushatha nivedhyam and big quantity of payasam should be made all pooja and vazhipad as per traditional rules and as per the advice of the temple thanthri

Parihara Poojakal:

- Perform 300 gayathri mathra with thilm 6000 panchakshari with ghee 1008 aghorha uthchadanam 1008 thrishtupp
- And bhadha avahahana as shyva, vyshnava, shaktheya do uthchadana

Result of the Deva Prashna:

After doing these parihara and other changes properly now the temple is one of the famous temple in kerala the people related to the temple are happy.

Conclusion:

If we follow Deva Prashna we will say from National Disasters like flood, cyclone, tsumami and famin. The rulers will govern us with happy and piece with prosperity

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